

Parks, Place, and Equity: Mapping access to different park typology in Britain's 20-minute neighbourhoods

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Summary

One-third of urban residents in Great Britain lack access to parks within a 20-minute round-trip of their home, but does this matter for public health? Our national analysis reveals disparities in park access across urban areas, with clear patterns developing between park-type combinations and deprivation levels. Future work will examine these relationships alongside cardiovascular disease mortality rates, revealing how different park types, from sports-focused to biodiversity-rich spaces might influence health outcomes. The findings could reshape how we plan and provide urban green spaces for public health.

KEYWORDS: objective measure, green space, deprivation, spatial data

1. Introduction

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a leading global cause of death, responsible for 17.9 million deaths (32%) in 2019 (WHO, 2022). The built environment significantly influences modifiable risk factors for CVD (Malambo et al., 2016). Studies show that approximately 20% of mortality is preventable through improved physical activity, air pollution, noise, heat, and green space access (Mueller et al., 2016).

Urban green space (UGS) has emerged as a key research focus for CVD mortality, though findings have been inconsistent (Yang et al., 2021). This inconsistency partly stems from varied UGS definitions and measurement approaches (Taylor and Hochuli, 2017). While commonly used methods like the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) provide standardised vegetation measurements (Martinez and Labib, 2023), they fail to capture specific characteristics, quality, or functions of green spaces. More detailed analyses using UGS morphology such as park size, configuration, and subjective qualities have revealed links to all-cause mortality (Wang and Tassinari, 2019), though these measures still don't capture functional aspects (Ngom et al., 2016).

The aims of this study are to a) use park typology, which classes park function by multiple qualities, to examine inequalities in park accessibility and b) determine if CVD mortality is associated with access to park typology. This study employs a national park typology for Great Britain (Hepburn et al., under review) that objectively measures park types and their functions across all urban parks in Great Britain, as defined in the Ordnance Survey's (OS) Open Greenspace dataset. This approach clusters parks based on their qualities rather than assigning hierarchical quality ratings, building on work by Knobel et al.

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(2019). Focusing on public parks is strategically important, as they are the most visited green spaces by urban residents across the UK (Natural England, 2019). The study also incorporates the concept of 20-minute neighbourhoods (20mn) (Giles-Corti et al., 2016; Markevych et al., 2017), an increasingly adopted urban planning framework. By combining advanced park classification methods with contemporary accessibility metrics, this study examines associations between different types and functions of urban greenspace within 20-minute neighbourhoods linking it to deprivation and cardiovascular disease mortality across Great Britain.

2. Methodology

For our methodology we utilised multiple national-scale datasets. We used secondary data created by Hepburn et al. (in review), which created GB-wide park typology, classing parks into six types; *Basic*, *Biodiversity*, *Amenity*-focused, *Comprehensive*, *Sports*-focused, and *Zero* Park. In addition to park typology, this analysis incorporated data from MasterMap Highways and census data (Office for National Statistics, National Records of Scotland). Sampling was restricted to urban local authority boundaries identified using Functional Urban Areas (FUAs). Socioeconomic assessment employed the Composite 2020 GB Index of Multiple Deprivation (Parsons, 2021) at the Lower Super Output Area (LSOA) level.

We derived park access points from the OS access point dataset in addition to overlaying multiple transport network layers (roads, paths, and cycle paths) on park geometries to create a more comprehensive dataset. This enhanced methodology captured complex access scenarios, such as reaching different park types by travelling through intermediate parks. Using the OS code-point dataset for each postcode, an 800m (equivalent to a 20 minute round-trip) buffer was created using the OS road and paths network from OS Highways; creating accessibility polygons for each postcode which corresponds as its 20mn.

For each urban postcode within the 20mn dataset, three key metrics were calculated:

1. Number of unique accessible parks
2. Types of parks accessible (binary measure)
3. Combinations of different park types available to residents

The accessibility analysis assigned park types to postcodes based on whether their 20mn buffer intersected with the park access points we created. This binary approach focused on whether residents could access different types of parks within their 20-minute neighbourhood, rather than counting the number of possible routes. To avoid double-counting parks with shared boundaries, access points were allocated the unique reference of the parks they served, providing a more accurate representation of park accessibility.

3. Preliminary Results

Analysis of park-type combinations across Great Britain's urban 20mn revealed significant disparities in park access. The most striking finding is that 12.1 million residents (32.9% of the urban population) have no access to parks within their 20mn. Single-type park access dominates the most common combinations, with *Basic* parks serving 4.5 million urban residents (12.3%) and *Biodiversity* parks serving 3.2 million urban residents (8.9%).

Sports and *Comprehensive* parks alone each serve approximately 1.8 million residents (5% each). The first multiple park-type combination appears sixth in frequency, with a *Basic & Biodiversity* park mix

servicing 1.8 million residents (4.9%). Notably, *Amenity* parks alone (1.6 million residents, 4.5%) are less common than the *Basic & Biodiversity* combination, suggesting these more frequently coincide in neighbourhoods than *Amenity* parks alone.

When examining park access across deprivation deciles, clear insights emerge (Figure 1). While having no park access ranks first across all deciles (top row), there are notable differences in second-ranked access (second row). In less deprived areas (deciles 8-10) have access to *Biodiversity* parks, while more deprived areas (decile 1 to 7) have *Basic* parks. *Sports* parks feature prominently (ranking third and fourth) in the most deprived areas (deciles 1-2) but do not appear in the top 5 rankings for less deprived areas (deciles 7–10). Furthermore, more deprived 20mn (deciles 1-4) show a greater diversity of combined park types, with combinations like *Basic & Biodiversity* and *Basic & Sport* appearing in their top 5, a pattern not observed in less deprived areas. These findings suggest that while overall park access varies across deprivation levels.

Figure 1 The top five most common combinations of park types accessible across deprivation deciles. Population derived from postcodes linked to LSOA-level deprivation metrics.

4. Next Steps

These preliminary results reveal important insights into park access and type distribution across Great Britain's urban areas by deprivation. However, the next step is to examine how these park-type combinations and access patterns relate to CVD mortality rates. By linking our park type accessibility data with CVD mortality data at the LSOA level, we can investigate whether specific park types or combinations in 20mn are associated with different CVD mortality outcomes.

This analysis will be particularly valuable given the varying park access patterns we have identified across deprivation deciles, as it may reveal whether certain park types or combinations could help mitigate CVD risk in areas of higher deprivation. Furthermore, our detailed categorisation of park types and access points will allow us to move beyond simple provision measures of green space, which treat all greenspace as equal, to understand whether park functions (such as sports facilities or biodiversity features) have stronger associations with CVD outcomes. This more nuanced analysis could provide valuable evidence to inform both public health interventions and urban planning policies aimed at reducing CVD mortality through strategic park provision and enhancement.

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